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TEACHING PROBLEM SOLVING SKILLS BY STRATEGY TRAININGS IN PHYSICS

K. Plicht¹

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0099-3001
Hochschule Ruhr West, University of Applied Sciences
Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany

H. Härtig

ORCID ID 0000-0002-6171-9284
Universität Duisburg-Essen
Essen, Germany

A. Dorschu

ORCID ID 0000-0002-7307-7389
Hochschule Ruhr West, University of Applied Sciences
Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays the expectations and requirements for engineers keep changing and involve besides technical, interdisciplinary and project management competencies, in particular problem solving skills [1].

It has been shown that implicit teaching of problem solving strategies fails. The results are missing approaches, no linkage to the existing knowledge and the failure of a solution. [2]

However, there is a very well evaluated state of research how novices and experts solve physics problems. Experts use problem schemes, which include heuristics and exemplary problems that ease the process of generating proper solutions and make the process much less error-prone. [3]

Therefore, the aim of this study is to develop a strategy training, which contains a strategy exercise and adjusted learning material to promote the problem solving competence of first year engineering students.

To implement such a strategy training in the regular physics exercise, a manual concerning different task characteristics has been developed. The resulting categories have been used to create a compilation of tasks, which are suitable for analysing the fitting heuristics. To measure the effect of the new learning material and the strategy training a 2x2-design was chosen to examine the influence of either one of those variables. The pre-post-evaluation will focus on questionnaires considering the stages of the problem solving process.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
K. Plicht
katja.plicht@hs-ruhwest.de

1. INTRODUCTION

Since problem solving competence in general is one of the most central requirements for engineers [1], it is reasonable to promote this skill as early as possible. At the beginning of various engineering study programs students attend physics courses, which often include weekly exercise assignments. These physics exercises represent knowledge-based problems, which are intended to train the problem solving competence.

Novices in physics thereby use an inefficient plug-and-chuck-procedure by searching for a suitable formula for the wanted variable [4]. This approach prevents a focused strategy that is a condition for a more efficient and understanding way of working [4]. For this reason it is necessary to teach problem solving strategies in an explicit way [2].

1.1 Knowledge-based problem solving

Typical physics tasks can be described by Friege's model of knowledge-based problem solving. The model considers in particular the difference between the solution process of experts and novices. Therefore experts are able to use problem schemes, which contain different solution approaches and heuristics of the corresponding physics concept. That's why they are able to use structural knowledge for the elaboration of a task. In contrast novices don't have those problem schemes yet, so that they have to solve a great number of exemplary problems to develop them. The elaboration of a solution without problem schemes is also very error-prone. [3]

Fig. 1 Model of knowledge-based problem solving by Friege [3], translated

Since weak problem solvers fail more often because of the planning phase and strong problem solvers fail in particular because of careless mistakes, it is questionable, if their ability to consider the deep structure of a task influences the problem solving strategy in general [5].

In addition, first year students start with very heterogeneous backgrounds of subject knowledge and problem solving skills, so that they don't achieve satisfactory problem solving strategies at the end of the semester [6]. It has to be evaluated whether the guidance of a reflection process will be able to establish the needed problem schemes.

1.2 Worked-Examples

A well established way of focusing on the principles behind a given problem, is to use worked-examples [7]. This enables a learning process which starts with learning aids that can be removed over time in the sense of a scaffolding approach. Whereas learning from worked-examples is very effective for the initial acquisition of cognitive skills in well structured-domains like physics [7], the purpose is to achieve an independent approach of problem solving in the end. Since the effectiveness of this method depends mainly on the self-explanation of the learners [8], it is important to initiate this aspect by using additional prompts. Consequently the use of worked-examples with well adjusted prompts in the beginning and fading learning aids during the semester allow a guided structure that leads to independent problem solving of the students and reduces unnecessary cognitive load.

2. STUDY APPROACH

Because of the students' lacking strategical methods to solve physics tasks, these will be developed through an exercise concept, which focuses on generating problem schemes. This exercise consists of two complementary interventions. On one hand a strategy exercise will be implemented, which instructs a reflection process on the students' methodological approach, on the other hand learning material will be designed, which uses worked examples and allows a reasonable handling of surface and deep structure characteristics.

The main approach of this study is to examine the influence of both strategy exercise and prestructured learning material on the problem solving competence of first year engineer students.

3. METHOD AND DESIGN

Since there are two different independent variables in this study, it is necessary to evaluate the influence of each aspect individually. Therefore a 2x2-design has been chosen. This means that there are four different exercise groups in which all combinations of the intervention are realised (Fig. 2). The intervention is implemented in the regular physics exercise related to the given lecture. Additionally a new compulsory exercise is established to ensure that all groups deal with the corresponding material to the same extent. During the exercise the students work on their learning material and

		Designed Learning Material	
		No	Yes
Strategy Exercise	No	Group I	Group II
	Yes	Group III	Group IV

Fig. 2. 2x2-Design of the intervention

have the option to ask subject related questions. Nevertheless there is no instructional aspect that influences the process. At the end of each exercise the students submit their work to receive individual feedback and achieve the qualification for the final exam. This framework ensures the necessary commitment of the students.

4. LEARNING MATERIAL

4.1 Task characteristics

In order to create a functioning strategy training, suitable tasks must be generated first. Since the specific problem schemes include corresponding problem types, solution approaches and heuristics, the tasks need to be organized according to the referring deep structure. Therefore it's necessary to develop a system that measures these task features. For this reason all complexity producing characteristics were summarized in a manual for the construction of the new tasks. Those characteristics relate to both surface and deep structure.

Table 1. Varied Task Characteristics

Task Characteristic	Function	Categories
Subject Content	Identifying tasks with mixed contents or multiple solutions	kinematics, forces, energy, momentum
Solution Approach	Generating similar deep structures	Top categories (with 66 subcategories): mathematical supplement, uniform motion, motion with constant acceleration, multidimensional motion, circular motion, forces, energy, momentum, rotation
Hierarchical Complexity	Increase during the semester and each content area	basic process description, basic linear causality, adapted process description, adapted linear causality, composed multivariate interdependence, multivariate interdependence
Scaffolding	Scaffolding during the semester	Subcategories: Number of intermediate tasks, standardised complexity, Scaffolding-Index
Mathematization	Increase of mathematization	no mathematization, calculation, converting, handling functional relations, modelling
Possible Solutions	Identifying tasks to illustrate advantages and disadvantages of different possible solution approaches	One solution, multiple solutions, one preferred solution

The dimension ‘subject content’ includes the three areas of the lecture: kinematics, forces and the conservation of energy and momentum.

The ‘hierarchical complexity’ leaned on the model of Bernholt [9] was adapted in order to consider the used learning tasks. The complexity increases gradually during the semester.

The category ‘Scaffolding’ measures the number of learning aids in relation to the corresponding complexity of every task. The final Scaffolding-Index determines the average standardised complexity per exercise sheet and increases during the semester.

The dimension ‘possible solutions’ indicates, if there are multiple ways to solve the given problem and if one of those possibilities should be preferred. This dimension is relevant to identify tasks, which can be used to reflect upon the advantages of different approaches to the same problem. This aspect will be considered in the continuing strategy exercise (s. Chapter 5).

The characteristics that function as control variables and are kept constant on one level are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Controlled Task Characteristics

Task Characteristic	Categories
<i>Subject Level</i>	school knowledge, deepened knowledge, university knowledge
<i>Subtasks</i>	No subtasks, interdependent subtasks, independent subtasks
<i>Type of Task Information</i>	Text, picture, graphic, table, diagram, numbers, others
<i>Relevance of Task Information</i>	only solution relevant, additional text information, additional other information
<i>Readability (LIX) [10]</i>	Values between 0 and 100

The current state of research has shown that the contextualization can hardly be determined by the present models. According to this, a prior investigation on this topic is considered for the pilot testing.

4.2 Developing new tasks

Since most of the described characteristics are control variables, because they would be complexity producing, the corresponding levels are kept constant. The features that are varied in this research are subject content, hierarchical complexity, scaffolding and solution approach. The subject content differs by the three main topics and the hierarchical complexity increases during each topic and the whole semester.

The main part of the construction was to build tasks with the same deep structure. To be able to teach the heuristics to the essential physics problems, it is necessary that the similarity of the deep structure is as high as possible. Since the novices have less experience with physics problems, the classification of problems and solution approaches was chosen as specific as possible. In order to compare the deep structure of the tasks, every solution was rated as a combination of solution approaches. Because of their specificity they only represent a part of the solution or the superior problem type, so that the complete problem can be represented as a sum of the corresponding solution approaches. Therefore the dimension 'solution approach' was developed.

To illustrate the described procedure an example is presented below.

Ball throw

A ball is thrown vertically. The discharge altitude is $y_0 = 1,5\text{m}$ and the initial velocity $v_0 = 15\frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$.

- a) Calculate when the ball will reach the highest point
- b) Calculate the maximum altitude y_s it will reach.
- c) Calculate when the ball hits the ground.
- d) Calculate when it is 6m above the ground.
- e) Calculate when the ball will return to its initial height on the way down.
- f) Plot the velocity v and the current altitude y as a function of t .

The example contains the following solution approaches:

Vertical throw, Calculation of a specific time (e.g. fall time), graphical illustration of the location of a motion with constant acceleration, graphical illustration of the velocity of a motion with constant acceleration

Note: The specific solution approach *vertical throw* contains another solution approach *using the equation of a motion with constant acceleration $s(t)$* , which is otherwise recorded separately.

By using this classification, it is possible to represent the deep structure of each task and to compare the necessary solution steps. Consequently, the different problems can be easily adjusted to be more or less alike, depending on the respective phase of the semester. Therefore the tasks in the beginning have the purpose to understand the underlying problem type, whereas the later ones enable the ability to identify and transfer a suitable solution approach to a modified problem.

4.3 Worked examples

Besides the main structure of each used task, there is also a worked example at the beginning of every exercise sheet. The worked example consists of a problem, its explained solution and a compilation of prompts. The prompts' function is to outline

the important explanation steps of each problem type to ease the following solution of the regular tasks with the same deep structure. The combination of self-explaining and explicit strategy exercise aims for synergetic effects.

5. STRATEGY EXERCISE

The strategy exercise represents the second part of this studys' intervention. Because of the 2x2-design, there are two groups that participate in the strategy training. One of them works with the developed learning material the other one doesn't.

5.1 Learning Outcomes

To illustrate the specific design of the strategy exercise, the related learning outcomes are listed below (Table 3).

Table 3. Learning outcomes

The students are able to...
...reflect on their methodological proceeding of solving physics tasks and name the strengths and weaknesses of their actions.
...name the additional value of a strategical procedure compared with the plug-and-chuck-procedure.
...name and use the relevant problem schemes consisting of problem type and heuristic.
...name the typical task characteristics of the relevant problem types and identify them in corresponding tasks.
...name and use the solution approaches of the relevant problem types.
...match tasks by their knowledge about problem schemes to a corresponding solution approach.
...decide by their knowledge about problem schemes, if a heuristic of a certain content area is suitable for a solution.

The subject related learning outcomes apply to each of the different content areas.

5.2 Teaching Method

In order to achieve these aims the teaching of problem solving strategies is realized in an explicit way.

At the beginning the students have to solve different problems with similar surface characteristics and a different deep structure. To illustrate the limits of the familiar formulas and strategies, only one of the problems can be solved by the current knowledge. This demonstrates the necessity of a more reliable procedure.

Subsequently one task will be used to abstract the referring solution approaches, problem type and typical task characteristics. In the following step the students will perform

this procedure on their own. The result will be an overview of the relevant aspects for each topic. To ensure the active use of the generated meta structures, the students match the prepared tasks to the related features. That way they train the identification of the established schemes in the actual realization.

To strengthen a systematic approach the students participate in little quizzes on deciding if a certain heuristic fits the given task and to specify the corresponding problem type and solution approach.

Therefore the strategy exercise consists of the following elements:

Table 4. Overview of the strategy training

Teaching Subject	Teaching method	Example
Awareness of the necessity of a reliable strategy	Produce a cognitive conflict by using various problem types which don't fit the current state of knowledge	Problems that describe different motion types, including some that are not known yet
Knowledge about different solution approaches	Abstracting the solution approaches of one task as a prototype to enable the transfer to further examples	A problem type in kinematics: e.g. horizontal throw
Knowledge about different problem types	Abstracting the problem type of one task as a prototype to enable the transfer to further examples	A solution approach in kinematics: e.g. $y(t) = 0$ to calculate a fall time
Knowledge about typical task characteristics	Abstracting the typical characteristics of one task as a prototype to enable the transfer to further examples	a task characteristic of a horizontal throw is a horizontal initial velocity
Knowledge about different heuristics	Generating the heuristic of one concept by abstracting the parallels of the procedures for the different problem types	The heuristic for kinematics starts with the identification of the given type of motion.

6. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Since the implementation of the described intervention won't be piloted until the next semester, there are only results concerning the theoretical analysis that has been made. For now the objectivity of the underlying rating manual was evaluated by the rating of the current task collection of the institute (91 tasks). The dimension 'Scaffolding' could not be examined yet, since it only relates to the new tasks. The interrater reliabilities of the three raters are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Interrater reliability of the examined task characteristics

Task Characteristic	Interrater Reliability	Significance
	κ	p
Subject Content	.61 - .86	.000
Solution Approach	.76 - .95	.000
Subject Level	.89	.000
Hierarchical Complexity	.88 - .91	.000
Possible Solutions	.94	.000
Mathematization	.96	.000
Subtasks	.95	.000
Type of Task Information	.73 - 1.0	.000
Relevance of Task Information	.80	.000
Readability (LIX) [10]	1.0	.000

Since the interrater reliability is between $\kappa = .61$ and $\kappa = 1.00$ the objectivity of the manual can be accepted.

7. SUMMARY AND PERSPECTIVE

The problem solving skill is one of the essential requirements for a modern engineer. Most engineering programs start with a physics course at the very beginning, where currently the use of fitting strategies are missing. Therefore the knowledge about problem schemes of experts in knowledge-based problem solving is used to design an intervention that teaches content related approaches as well as general heuristics to improve the students' problem solving competence.

The designed learning material combines worked-examples and a task compilation, which considers the referring deep structure. The strategy exercise teaches knowledge about certain problem types and their solution approaches to focus on a more general heuristics, which allows an independent problem solving process.

The analysis of relevant task characteristics was operationalized as a rating manual. Its objectivity could be verified by a sufficient interrater reliability. The deep structure of the new tasks was aligned with these aspects.

The next step will be a pilot phase, which includes the implementation of both interventions. Additionally the necessary testing instruments will be examined. This includes prior knowledge in physics and mathematics, linguistic competence and problem solving performance. For a differentiated analysis a test concerning the declarative knowledge of problem schemes will be developed.

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